

Career Development Plan

Project Number: 101066739

Project Acronym: DTADD

Project Title: Digital Twin Anomaly Detection Decision-Making for Bridge Management

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1 Preamble

1.1 Brief overview of research project and major accomplishments expected

Bridge infrastructure in Europe has great economic, social, and cultural value. Nevertheless, many of the assets which are part of this network are in poor condition, which has been recently evidenced by the collapse of several bridges. The available human and economic resources are simply not enough to repair, maintain or replace all bridges part of the European network. Therefore, improvements on the current bridge management and operation system are urgently needed.

During this fellowship an open-source digital twin anomaly detection decision-making tool will be developed to support the preventive conservation of existing bridges in Europe. This innovative tool will improve the bridge management by aiding the implementation of a reliability-based bridge management approach (RBBMA), thus contributing to bridge cultural heritage (CH) conservation and sustainability by extending their service life and reducing management costs.

The DTADD fellowship has two specific objectives. The first objective is to build digital twin (DT) models of heritage/conventional bridges to assess and identify the highest performing anomaly detection algorithm (ADA) for damage and/or significant decay detection. Its second objective is to develop an ADA-informed open-source decision-making tool based on a RBBMA, to assess the need for bridge intervention while explicitly considering the bridge's CH value.

This fellowship will be carried out mainly at OsloMet, Norway, with a six-month secondment at TU Delft, Netherlands. The research experience, skills and knowledge obtained during the fellowship will help the experienced researcher (ER) to become a leading international expert on the conservation of bridges and will aid him to achieve his goal of becoming an independent researcher and obtaining a tenure track position.

Furthermore, this fellowship is aligned with the Transport action of the European Green Deal¹ as well as with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)².

1.2 Long-term career objectives

1.2.1 Goals

The long-term career objective (over 5 years) of the ER is to obtain a tenure track Assistant Professor position at a recognized University (top 200 in the [QS World University Rankings for Engineering - Civil and Structural 2022](#)) in one of the top 20 Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Better Life Index countries (see Figure 1, [OECD Better Life Index](#)).

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/transport-and-green-deal_en

² <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

Figure 1. OECD Better Life Index countries organized by Rank (the higher the rank, the better life quality).

1.2.2 What further research activity or other training is needed to attain these goals?

- The ER needs to increase his publication record (more peer reviewed journal papers published on Q1 and high IF journals, as well as peer reviewed and indexed conference papers and book chapters).
- The ER needs to increase his teaching and supervising experience (present lectures, supervise Master and PhD thesis, obtain formal teaching accreditation).
- The ER needs to strengthen his professional network and participate in extra academic activities (such as organization of conferences, participation in peer reviewing and editorial tasks, involvement with research groups and specialized research committees).
- The ER needs to receive training regarding the preparation of advanced research proposals to obtain funding for future academic/research career progression (European Research Council (ERC), National Science and Research Councils, etc.).

2 Year 1 Short Term Objectives

2.1 Research results

2.1.1 Anticipated publications

- Peer reviewed journal paper published in the Frontier's Insights: Frontiers in Built Environment 2023 Research Topic ([Insights: Frontiers in Built Environment | Frontiers Research Topic](#)).
- Peer reviewed journal paper published in Frontier's Methods and Applications in Computational Methods in Structural Engineering 2023 Research Topic ([Methods and Applications in Computational Methods in Structural Engineering | Frontiers Research Topic \(frontiersin.org\)](#)).
- Peer reviewed journal paper published in MDPI Buildings ([Buildings | An Open Access Journal from MDPI](#)).
- Peer reviewed journal paper published in ASCE Journal of Bridge Engineering ([Journal of Bridge Engineering | ASCE Library](#)).
- Peer reviewed journal paper published in ASCE Journal of Civil Engineering Education ([Journal of Civil Engineering Education | ASCE Library](#)).

2.1.2 Anticipated conference, workshop attendance, courses, and/or seminar presentations

- Attendance to the 2023 Oslo Big Data Day emerging tech conference, Oslo, Norway ([2023 OBDD](#)).
- Present paper at the 9th International Conference on Computational Methods in Structural Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering (COMPDYN 2023), Athens, Greece ([COMPDYN 2023 / 9th International Conference on Computational Methods in Structural Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering](#)).
- Present paper at the 5th International Conference on Uncertainty Quantification in Computational Science and Engineering, Athens, Greece ([UNCECOMP 2023 / 5th International Conference on Uncertainty Quantification in Computational Science and Engineering](#)).
- Present paper at the 15th International Conference on Evolutionary and Deterministic Methods for Design, Optimization and Control, Crete, Greece ([EUROGEN 2023 / 15th International Conference on Evolutionary and Deterministic Methods for Design, Optimization and Control](#)).

2.2 Research skills and techniques

2.2.1 Training in specific new areas, or technical expertise etc.

- To complete the Structural Health Monitoring for integrity management of civil structures and infrastructures at the PhD Program in Architecture, Built Environment and Construction Engineering, Politecnico di Milano, Italy ([Manifesti Dottorato \(polimi.it\)](#)).
- To complete the 8th CISM-ECCOMAS Advanced School on Scientific Machine Learning in Design Optimization Advanced Course ([8th CISM-ECCOMAS Advanced School on Scientific Machine Learning in Design Optimization • CISM](#)).

2.2.2 Research specific training

- Completion of Peer Review Excellence online course delivered by IOP Publishing ([Peer Review Excellence - Peer Review Excellence](#)).
- Attendance to the Pilot Track Masterclass Series provided at Oslo Metropolitan University.

2.3 Research management

- None.

2.4 Communication skills:

- Enrol in the Norwegian level A1 course available for OsloMet staff ([Norwegian course for employees, beginners level A1](#)).

2.5 Other professional training (course work, teaching activity)

- Lecturing at the Concrete Design course at OsloMet ([Studyinfo subject BYTS2500 2022 HØST - minside \(oslomet.no\)](#)).
- Lecturing at the FEM course at OsloMet ([MABY4100 Finite Element Method in Structural Analysis](#)).
- Co-supervising the MSc thesis of Merhawi Misgina on Structural Health Monitoring.

- Supervise the European Project Semester (EPS) project titled “Tilting Table Tests of Masonry Assemblies” at Oslo Metropolitan University ([Welcome | European Project Semester](#)).

2.6 Anticipated networking opportunities

- Networking at the different events the ER will participate, i.e., Departmental meetings, conferences, and workshops.

2.7 Other activities (community, etc) with professional relevance

- Participation at the 2023 European Researchers’ Night ([2022 European Researchers’ Night](#)) and Pint of Science Global Science Festival ([Pint of Science](#)).

3 Year 2 Short Term Objectives

3.1 Research results

3.1.1 Anticipated publications

- Open access peer-reviewed journals such as The Baltic Journal of Road and Bridge Engineering and Engineering Structures and Technologies.

3.1.2 Anticipated conference, workshop attendance, courses, and/or seminar presentations

- Presenting scientific dissemination papers at the IABSE and IABMAS annual conferences.
- Organization and facilitation of co-design, co-creation and co-assessment workshop with relevant bridge operation and management stakeholders (Statens Vegvesen and Rijkswaterstaat).

3.2 Research skills and techniques

3.2.1 Training in specific new areas, or technical expertise etc.

- Participate in the 2023 edition of the EUROSTRUCT Training School ([Training School Archives - EUROSTRUCT](#)).

3.2.2 Research specific training

- Course or seminar offered at TU Delft about the proposal preparation and application process of an ERC or NWO project.

3.3 Research management

- Enrol in the Introductory Leading Research Projects course at Oslo Metropolitan University ([Leading research projects: Introductory course - minside \(oslomet.no\)](#)).

3.4 Communication skills:

- Enrol in the Norwegian level A2 course available for OsloMet staff ([Norwegian course for employees, beginners’ level A2](#)).

3.5 Other professional training (course work, teaching activity)

- Co-supervising a MSc thesis of a student at TU Delft.

3.6 Anticipated networking opportunities

- Networking at the different events the ER will participate, i.e., Departmental meetings, conferences, and workshops.

3.7 Other activities (community, etc) with professional relevance

- Participation at the 2024 European Researchers' Night ([2022 European Researchers' Night](#)) and Pint of Science Global Science Festival ([Pint of Science](#)).

References

Annex A

Table 1. History of changes.

Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	April 2023	Initial version.

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